

The effect of crystallites on the rheological properties of micro-phase separated PVC-PBA-PVC tri-block copolymers obtained by Single Electron Transfer-Degenerative Chain Transfer Living Radical Polymerization

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14 **The effect of crystallites on the rheological properties of micro-**
15 **phase separated PVC-PBA-PVC tri-block copolymers obtained**
16 **by Single Electron Transfer-Degenerative Chain Transfer Living**
17 **Radical Polymerization**
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Abstract

Linear and non linear rheological properties of PVC-PBA-PVC tri-blocks of different compositions, obtained by Single Electron Transfer-Degenerative Chain Transfer Living Radical Polymerization (STE-DTLRP), are investigated, focusing on the effect of crystallites. DMTA results show the existence of two glass transition temperatures, denoting a microphase segregation. But, rather than phase separation, it is the presence of two types of crystals that melt at $T_{m1}=127^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 0.8^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $T_{m2}=185^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively, the factor which determines the rheological response of the copolymers. To the difference with PVC homopolymers, extrusion flow measurements at very low temperatures ($T=100^{\circ}\text{C}$) are possible with the copolymers. A change in the viscosity-temperature dependence is remarked, below and above the lowest melting temperature. Notwithstanding the microphase separation and the presence of crystallites, experiments carried out in conditions similar to industrial processing, reveal a remarkable viscosity reduction for our copolymers with respect to PVC obtained by STE-DTLRP, conventional PVC and PVC/DOP compounds. Extrudates free of surface instabilities are obtained at low extrusion temperatures such as 90-100°C.

Introduction

It is nowadays well known that Living Radical Polymerization (LRP) constitutes a reliable alternative to effectively control the molecular architecture of polymers. This technique allows preparing new-tailor made polymers with complex macrostructures that are inaccessible by conventional free radical polymerization method. Functionalised polymers with controlled molecular weight, narrow poly-dispersities and long-lived chains that can be further activated, are obtained with this polymerization method.

The main processes reported in the literature are via metal catalyzed LRP [1,2], degenerative transfer (DT) [3,4] and reversible addition-fragmentation chain transfer (RAFT) [5].

In the particular case of PVC, the new methodology discovered by Percec et al. named Single Electron Transfer-Degenerative Chain Transfer Living Radical Polymerization (SET- DTLRP) opens the door to obtain block copolymers, polymerizing vinyl chloride "in situ" in a macro-radical of another monomer or vice versa [6,7,8]. This method, that does not involve particular difficulties to be deployed at industrial level, has been recently employed by Rocha et al. for the synthesis of PVC based block copolymers containing different segments of poly (hydroxipropyl acrylate) [9].

A punctual and very interesting success of this technology concerns the synthesis of tri-block copolymers (ABA) of poly(vinyl chloride) (PVC) and poly(*n*-butyl acrylate) (PBA), that is, PVC-*b*-PBA-*b*-PVC [10,11]. This represents a significant advance with respect to block PVC-PBA copolymers prepared *via* radical block polymerization [12]

One specific issue of PVC is that its particles have crystallites of varying sizes, which only melt completely above approximately 230°C [13,14]. This factor is of crucial importance for industrial processing, because the low thermal stability of this polymer obliges to process it in a partially crystalline state. To avoid this difficulty, plasticisers such as diethyl- (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (more known as DOP) have been traditionally used, but the migration of these low molecular weight molecules cause salubriousness problems. Plasticisation or reduction of the glass transition temperature, T_g , of PVC has been also reached by means of blends (for instance with EVA copolymer) or by internal plasticisation with

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3 PBA in PVC-PBA copolymers obtained by radical block polymerization [12] or in
4 PVC-PBA-PVC triblock copolymers obtained by LRP [15,16,17]. The route of
5 graft polymerization of PVC with acrylic monomers, including butyl acrylate, by
6 in situ polymerization, has been explored as well [18,19,20]. Thermal, dynamic
7 mechanical, rheological and mechanical properties of these copolymers have
8 been studied, but the effect of the eventual presence of crystallites on the
9 thermal and rheological features of PVC-PBA-PVC triblock copolymers has not
10 been contemplated, so far. Furthermore, the microphase separation that can be
11 expected in block copolymers which contain segments with different solubility
12 parameters [21], as is the case of PVC and PBA, has not been investigated yet,
13 at least from the point of view of its rheological repercussions.
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21 Having regard to this state of the art, the principal aim of this paper is to
22 investigate the rheological properties of PVC-PBA-PVC tri-blocks obtained by
23 SET- DTLRP, analyzing the effect phase separation and crystallites.
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28 **Experimental Part**

29 **Materials**

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31 The following reagents were used to obtain the copolymers: Iodoform (99%
32 purity) purchased from Ajay-SQM Group; sodium dithionate (85% purity),
33 cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (99% purity) and sodium bicarbonate (99%
34 purity) purchased from Sigma-Aldrich; n-butylacrylate (n-BA) from ARKEMA
35 and PVA from Synthomer.
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44 **Polymerization procedure and samples preparation**

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46 As an example of the procedure employed to obtain the block copolymers
47 analyzed in this study, the process of obtaining the block-copolymer 35PVC-
48 30PBA-PVC35 is described below.
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51 In a reactor of 7.5 liter capacity, equipped with a stirrer, cooling/heating jacket,
52 injection pipette, load pump and a computerized control system, 3500 g of
53 deionized water, 160.8 g of a 5.8 wt% solution of a polyvinyl alcohol with a
54 hydrolysis degree of 72.5% in deionized water, 0.35 g of sodium bicarbonate
55 and 1.94 g of iodoform, were loaded. Once the reactor was closed and the
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3 stirrer was connected at 100 rpm, vacuum was applied (0.1 bar) during 5 min.
4 This operation was repeated twice, and finally vacuum was applied for 5 min.
5 more. After, the reactor was pressured with nitrogen to avoid the entrance of
6 oxygen, the stirrer speed was increased to 450 rpm and 312.5g of butylacrylate
7 were loaded. When a temperature of 35°C was reached, a solution of 6.0 g of
8 sodium dithionite (85% purity) in 50 mL of deionized water was injected to the
9 reactor. The reaction was maintained during 45 minutes. After this time, 938 g
10 of vinyl chloride were loaded from a pressured bottle and the reaction
11 temperature was increased to 42°C. When this temperature was reached, a 50
12 ml solution of 0.35 g of sodium bicarbonate, 0.287 g of cetyltrimethylammonium
13 bromide and 2 g of sodium dithionite (85% purity) was injected in the reactor.
14 The reaction was kept under the same conditions during 4 hours and after this
15 time, the unreacted vinyl chloride was removed by depressurizing the reactor.
16 Then, the obtained suspension was separated by filtration and washed three
17 times with deionized water. The product was dried with air at 60 °C on a
18 fluidized bed dryer until constant weight was obtained.

19 Before performing different kinds of experiments, pressed sheets were prepared
20 by formulating the obtained copolymers with 2 phr of a Ca/Zn stabilizer and 3
21 phr of epoxydized soy bean oil, wherein phr is an abbreviation for "parts per
22 hundred parts of resin". Formulations were homogenized in a two-roll mill at 160
23 °C and pressed at the same temperature.

24 A plasticised formulation obtained with a commercial PVC resin supplied by
25 ERCROS, S.A. Etinox 650 (k value 68) and 55 phr of 2-ethylhexyl phthalate
26 (DEHP) was prepared for comparison purposes
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33 **Characterization**

34 H^1 NMR spectra were obtained in a Bruker spectrometer (500 MHz) at room
35 temperature in deuterated tetrahydrofuran (THF- d_8).
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38 The 1H -NMR spectra of the 25PVC-50PBA-25PVC copolymer and free-radical
39 PVC are shown in Figure 1. The NMR spectrum of the 25PVC-50PBA-25PVC
40 copolymer shows the signals expected for the PBA and PVC. The resonances
41 of butyl fragment O-CH₂- CH₂- CH₂-CH₃ of PBA signal are located at 4.03,
42 1.6, 1.4 and 0.95 ppm respectively. The signals of the PBA methine protons of
43 main chain are situated at 2.3 ppm. The peaks characteristics of PVC are
44 shown between 4.2 and 4.7 ppm to -CHCl protons and between 2.0 and 2.5
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3 ppm to methine protons of PVC main chain. The success of this block
4 copolymerization is confirmed by the presence of active chain ends at ~6 ppm,
5 as can be seen in the magnification of the 5-7 ppm region of Figure 1. In spite of
6 their low concentration, the r and m-CHCl signals are detected at 6.04 and 6.13
7 ppm [22]. Finally, the ¹H NMR spectra of both samples show a signal of
8 structural defects at 5.86 and 5.77 ppm assigned to –CH=CH– moieties [7].
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14 The weight average molecular weight, M_w , and the number average molecular
15 weight, M_n , were determined by Size Exclusion Chromatography (SEC) in a
16 Waters 717 Autosampler, consisting of a pump, a refractive index detector, and
17 Waters Styragel (HR2, HR4, and HR6) columns. THF was used as eluent at a
18 flow rate of 1ml/min and temperature of 35°C. The SEC system was calibrated
19 with polystyrene narrow standards ranging from 580 to 395×10^3 g/mole and
20 were corrected with the Universal Calibration using Mark Houwink parameters
21 for PS: $K = 1.58 \times 10^{-4}$ mL/g, $\alpha(a) = 0.704$
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30 The corresponding compositions and molecular weights of the copolymers are
31 presented in Table I. This Table also includes the molecular parameters of a
32 FRP (free radical polymerized) commercial PVC suspension grade Etinox-650,
33 supplied by ERCROS S.A., which is used, as a plasticised compound, for
34 comparison purposes in the last part of the paper.
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39 2 phr of a stabilizer and 3 phr of epoxydated soy bean oil (wherein phr stands
40 for "parts per hundred parts of resin") were added to all the samples, which
41 were homogenized in a two-roll mill at 160°C and pressed at the same
42 temperature.
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46 47 **Thermal and rheological measurements**

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49 Dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) tests were performed in a Triton
50 Tritec 2000 equipment using rectangular specimens cut from compression-
51 molded sheets. The tests were performed at 1 Hz and at a heating rate of
52 4°C/min from -100°C to 120°C. The experiments were performed at least two
53 times to assure repetitiveness, in single cantilever bending mode. The tensile
54 elastic modulus E' and the loss tangent, $\tan \delta$, were investigated as a function
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3 of temperature.

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5 Thermal analysis data were completed by differential scanning calorimetry (Q-
6 2000 TA Instruments) under nitrogen. The compression-moulded samples were
7 tested from 50°C to 200°C at a scan rate of 10°C/min. All samples used for DSC
8 were around 10 mg and were sealed in an aluminium pan. The samples were
9 tested without erasing its previous thermal history.

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13 The viscoelastic behavior in the molten state was investigated using a ARG-2
14 rheometer with a parallel-plate fixture (25mm diameter), to conduct oscillatory
15 frequency sweep experiments in the linear regime at the temperatures indicated
16 in the Results and Discussion section. The dynamic viscoelastic functions,
17 shear elastic modulus, G' , and shear loss modulus, G'' , were obtained as a
18 function of frequency.
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23 Extrusion flow experiments were performed in a Göttfert 2002 rheometer using
24 a capillary die with $L/D=30/1$, at the temperatures and shear rates indicated in
25 Results and Discussion section. The viscosity curves, i.e. viscosity as a function
26 of shear rate, were obtained.
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30 31 32 33 **Results and Discussion**

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36 DMTA results of the PVC-PBA-PVC copolymers, as well as PVC and PBA
37 homopolymers, are displayed in Figure 2. The copolymers show two glass
38 transition temperatures detected by $\tan \delta$ peaks: One in the range -8°C to 0°C ,
39 and the other between 78°C and 80°C . On the other hand, the results of the
40 homopolymers reveal the glass transitions of PBA at -33°C and PVC at 90°C ,
41 respectively. Based on this DMTA data, we estimate that the lowest T_g should
42 be associated to the glass transition of PBA in PBA rich domains, and the
43 highest T_g to the glass transition of PVC in PVC rich domains. Certainly, the
44 lower glass transition of the copolymers ($T_g = -8$ to 0°C) is considerably above
45 the glass transition of PBA homopolymer ($T_g = -33^\circ\text{C}$), which can be due to the
46 hindering of the molecular motion caused by more rigid PVC. Our results of
47 Figure 2 differ from those of Coelho et al [16,17], who report a single broad
48 peak of $\tan \delta$ for PVC-PBA-PVC triblock copolymers obtained also by SET-
49 DTLRP. The existence of a single T_g for the copolymers, reported by Coelho et
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3 al, indicates the absence of microphase separation and constitutes a signal of
4 miscibility. Probably this disagreement in DMTA results is a consequence of
5 punctual differences in the experimental procedure employed (described in our
6 case in the Experimental Part) to obtain the copolymers. Actually, several
7 issues linked to the polymerization procedure, that can affect the interpretation
8 of the results, should be taken into account. We have considered, for instance,
9 the eventual presence of PBA mixed with the copolymer at the end of the
10 polymerization. In our copolymers this possibility is discarded, since NMR
11 results (not shown) of the samples after washing with ethanol, that would
12 remove PBA, indicate the same PBA proportion. Unfortunately, NMR analysis is
13 not sufficiently conclusive to discard the formation of PVC homopolymer due to
14 chain transfer reactions occurring during the second step of the
15 copolymerization. But, a study of the different degradation mechanisms of block
16 copolymers and blends, which is out of the scope of this paper, carried out in
17 our laboratory, leads us to assume that PVC homopolymer is not formed in our
18 polymerization process. In any case, the microphase segregation, denoted by
19 the two Tg-s of Figure 2, may be explained disregarding the presence of
20 homopolymers, because it is a logical consequence of the low thermodynamic
21 miscibility between PVC and PBA in the copolymer. This immiscibility, which
22 triggers phase segregation, was remarked many years ago by Overbergh [12]
23 for PVC-Poly(alkyl acrylate) and PVC-PBA block copolymers obtained by
24 radical block polymerization. The level of miscibility is estimated considering
25 segment-segment interaction parameter $\chi = (\delta_a - \delta_b)^2$, where $\delta_a = 21 \text{ (MPa)}^{1/2}$ and
26 $\delta_b = 18 \text{ (MPa)}^{1/2}$ are the solubility parameters of the respective PVC and PBA
27 chains [23]. Since the inverse of χ reflects the degree of affinity between the
28 segments [24], the high value obtained for our PVC-PBA-PVC copolymers
29 ($\chi = 9 \text{ Ma}$) leads us to assume that an organized microphase separation is very
30 likely to occur. Comparatively, very well known styrenic triblock copolymers,
31 such as Poly (Styrene-b-Butadiene-b-Styrene) (SBS), have lower interaction
32 parameter values ($\chi = 4 \text{ MPa}$ obtained from $\delta_a = 18 \text{ (MPa)}^{1/2}$ and $\delta_b = 16$
33 $\text{(MPa)}^{1/2}$ [24] and are actually microphase separated systems or self-assembled
34 systems in which an order at nanoscale is developed [25].
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3 Rheological techniques have turned to be a powerful tool to characterize the
4 spatial organisation and phase separation of block copolymers. As reported in
5 particular for styrenic copolymers [26,27,28,29] at temperatures below an order-
6 disorder transition, $T < T_{ODT}$, the presence of ordered microstructures alters the
7 terminal viscoelastic zone. Instead of the dependences $G' \propto \omega^2$ and $G'' \propto \omega$, with
8 $G'' > G'$, observed for homogeneous melts [30] a predominantly elastic response
9 (with $G' > G''$) is noticed in the microphase separated systems [31]. Heating the
10 block copolymer above its order-disorder temperature (T_{ODT}) microphase
11 separation is eliminated and the sample behaves like a homogeneous polymer
12 melt.
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20 However, in the case of PVC-PBA-PVC triblock copolymers, the rheological
21 analysis of the microphase separation and the order-disorder transition is far of
22 being an easy task. Actually, in our copolymers, the eventual existence of a
23 network of crystallites, characteristic of PVC samples, can mask the effect of
24 microphase phase separation. In fact, the alteration of the terminal zone
25 provoked either by microphase separation or by the microcrystalline structure of
26 PVC, is very similar. The crystallites act as physical crosslinking points, giving
27 rise to slightly frequency dependent dynamic moduli and $G' > G''$, even at
28 temperatures close to 200°C [32,33]. This is not surprising, considering that
29 PVC particles have crystallites of varying sizes with a broad melting range,
30 practically from 100°C to 230°C [13,14]. These literature results should be bore
31 in mind to interpret the dynamic viscoelastic data shown in Figure 3. Only poly
32 (butyl acrylate) homopolymer approaches to the results of a homogeneous melt,
33 with a well defined terminal zone characterized by a prevailing loss or viscous
34 modulus, over elastic modulus ($G'' > G'$). For the rest of the samples (not all
35 included in Figure 3, to avoid overlapping), the elastic modulus is predominant
36 over the loss modulus, which, as stated above, could be due either to
37 microphase separation or to the presence of a microcrystalline structure in the
38 PVC phase of the triblock copolymer.
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50 Confirming the latter hypothesis, DSC results, displayed in Figure 4, show
51 crystallinity traces for all the copolymers, including the 25PVC/50PBA/25PVC
52 composition, which contains the lower PVC amount among our samples. As
53 mentioned above, the presence of crystallites plays a fundamental role in the
54 rheological behaviour linked to industrial processing of PVC. But, so far, the
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3 existence of crystallites and its effect on the rheological response have not been
4 demonstrated for PVC-PBA copolymers. As shown in Figure 4, our DSC results
5 give account of two types of crystals for both, PVC and copolymers: Those that
6 melt at $T_{m1}=127^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 0.8^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the crystals that melt at $T_{m2}=185^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$.
7 These temperatures are taken at the maximum of the endotherms observed in
8 Figure 4. Since the rheological results of Figure 3 are obtained at $T=180^{\circ}\text{C}$, the
9 presence of crystals that melt at $185^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ justifies the predominantly elastic
10 response, $G'>G''$, observed in Figure 3 for all the samples, except for pure PBA.
11 The enthalpies of fusion and the estimated crystallinity degrees are shown in
12 Table II. The results indicate that the levels of crystallinity are very similar for
13 PVC homopolymer and for all the copolymers, which is compatible with the
14 aforementioned microphase separation. Unfortunately the relatively rapid
15 degradation of our copolymers (similar to that of PVC) makes impossible to
16 carry out rheological measurements at temperatures above the complete
17 melting of the crystallites.
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27 Therefore, the effect of the network formed by the crystallites on the viscoelastic
28 results can not be avoided. This impedes a dynamic viscoelastic analysis of the
29 ordered state of the microphase separated PVC-PBA-PVC triblock copolymers
30 and its order-disorder transition temperature.
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34 Extrusion flow measurements, in conditions similar to industrial processing, are
35 also conditioned by the DSC results of Figure 4 and Table II. This allows us
36 finding resemblances between the rheological response of our triblock
37 copolymers and the well studied extrusion rheology of PVC samples. It is known
38 [34,35,36,37,38,39] that PVC behaves rather like a filled polymer, owed to the
39 systematic presence of crystallites at the tests temperatures. A significant
40 difference, in favour of the copolymers, is that, owed to the viscosity reduction
41 associated with the copolymerization with PBA, temperatures considerably
42 lower than with PVC can be used in capillary extrusion experiments. As an
43 example of the obtained results, in Figure 5 the viscosity as a function of shear
44 rate for PVC and a representative triblock copolymer are presented at different
45 temperatures. The temperature limitations to obtain flow conditions suitable for
46 processing of PVC samples are due to the extremely high viscosities at low
47 temperatures (brought about by the presence of crystallites) and the
48 degradation at high temperatures. In this sense, the temperature range (from
49 160 to 190°C) at we are able to measure the viscosity of our PVC is an
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3 expected interval. But we remark that in the case of our copolymers, viscosities
4 can be measured at much lower temperatures and covering a wider
5 temperature range, from 100°C to 190°C. Reliable experiments can be carried
6 out even at 90°C, for 25PVC/50PBA/25PVC copolymer (not shown). This opens
7 the possibility of studying the rheological behaviour below the lower melting
8 temperature of the crystallites, $T_{m1}=127^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 0.8^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Figure 3). All the data fit
9 very well the Ostwald and de Waele [40] power law model $\eta \propto \dot{\gamma}^{n-1}$ (slope $n-1$ in
10 $\log \eta - \log \dot{\gamma}$ plots) where n is the pseudoplastic index that accounts for the
11 shear thinning degree. The samples are very shear thinning, with n values in
12 the range 0.35 -0.12, but no “plug flow”, produced as polymer melt slips in the
13 wall (which implies $n=0$), is observed. Our attempts to correlate the values of n
14 with temperature and/or copolymer composition have been fruitless.

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17 The particular effect of temperature on viscosity is analyzed using Arrhenius-like
18 plots, $\ln \eta$ versus $1/T$, at a constant shear rate. Such plots are presented in
19 Figure 6 for all the samples with the viscosities taken at a shear rate of 100 s^{-1} .
20 Similar results are obtained when viscosities are taken at other shear rates. The
21 data are fitted to straight lines which represent the equation:

$$22 \eta(T) = A \cdot e^{\frac{E_a}{RT}} \quad (1)$$

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25 where A is a constant, R is the gas constant and E_a is the activation energy of
26 flow. The application of this equation to the data of Figure 6 requires the
27 definition of two rheological zones for the copolymers, except for
28 25PVC/50PBA/25PVC sample. The fitting of the data of the copolymers to two
29 straight lines does make sense, considering the presence of crystals that melt in
30 the contemplated temperature range. The crossing of the lines is close to
31 $T=127^{\circ}\text{C}$, which coincides with the lower melting temperature, $T_{m1}=127^{\circ}\text{C}\pm$
32 0.8°C , defined through DSC measurements. In the literature [37,39], two flow
33 zones are defined for PVC, respectively above and below the highest melting
34 temperature of crystallites, T_{m2} . But, with our copolymers we can define a new
35 low temperature flow region that accounts for the presence of both, crystallites
36 that melt at T_{m1} and crystallites that melt at T_{m2} . This is a particular feature of
37 the triblock copolymers studied in this work, since in the case of PVC,
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3 rheological measurements at such low temperatures are not possible. The
4 activation energy of flow (slope of $\ln \eta^{-1}/T$ in Figure 6) in the lowest temperature
5 zone, below T_{m1} , is higher, due to the presence of both type of crystals. This is
6 compatible with an increase of the rigidity of the chain which it is known that, in
7 general, produces an enhancement of the activation energy of flow [41]. The
8 absence of any evidence of two flow regions for the sample that contains 50%
9 of PBA (a single straight line in Figure 6, which reflects only one E_a) is
10 explained considering that for this composition PBA passes to constitute the
11 continuous phase, as can be seen in the Transmission Electron Microscopy
12 image of Figure 7, concealing the crystalline nature of the dispersed PVC
13 phase. Moreover, the activation energy of flow of the 25PVC/50PBA/25PVC
14 copolymer, obtained from the single straight line of Figure 6, is $E_a = 21$ kJ/ mol
15 which agrees with the activation energy of PBA obtained in our laboratory.
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24 The rheological results obtained in the extrusion capillary rheometer
25 demonstrate the performing response of our triblock copolymers during
26 industrial extrusion processes. Viscosity curves are shown in Figure 8 for the
27 different samples. For comparison purposes, results of commercial rigid PVC
28 and plasticised PVC/DOP sample are also included. At the lowest temperature
29 allowed for pure PVC, $T=160^\circ\text{C}$, the viscosity reduction observed for the PVC-
30 PBA-PVC triblock copolymers is more severe than for PVC plasticised with 35%
31 DOP. In particular, the sample with the highest PBA content,
32 25PVC/50PBA/25PVC copolymer, brings about a viscosity reduction of more
33 than one decade. On the other hand, instabilities of the extrudates, which
34 appear in PVC samples under a wide range of temperatures and shear rates,
35 are avoided in the case of the copolymers, confirming the good processing
36 properties of the latter. As an example, in Figure 9 melt fracture distortion is
37 observed for a PVC extrudate obtained at $T=160^\circ\text{C}$ and a shear rate of 10s^{-1} ,
38 whereas a smooth extrudate is obtained with the copolymer
39 40PVC/20PBA/40PVC at $T=100^\circ\text{C}$ and 300s^{-1} .
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52 Conclusions

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54 Thermal and rheological properties of PVC-PBA-PVC copolymers obtained by
55 Single Electron Transfer-Degenerative Chain Transfer Living Radical
56 Polymerization are investigated. DMTA results show the existence of two glass
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3 transition temperatures, denoting a microphase segregation that responds to
4 the low thermodynamic miscibility between PVC and PBA,
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7 A dynamic linear viscoelastic analysis of the order state associated with
8 microphase separation is not possible, since the presence of two types of
9 crystals that melt at $T_{m1}=127^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 0.8^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $T_{m2}=185^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively,
10 disturbs the viscoelastic behaviour expected for microphase separated systems.
11 These crystallites, rather than phase separation, determine the rheological
12 response of the copolymers. To the difference with pure PVC, extrusion flow
13 measurements at very low temperatures ($T=100^{\circ}\text{C}$) are possible with PVC-
14 PBA-PVC copolymers. This allows observing a change in the viscosity-
15 temperature dependency below and above the lowest melting temperature
16 $T_{m1}=127^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 0.8^{\circ}\text{C}$.
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23 Notwithstanding the presence of microphase separation and crystallites, non-
24 linear viscosity results, obtained in conditions similar to industrial processing,
25 reveal a remarkable viscosity reduction for our copolymers with respect to PVC
26 obtained by STE-DTLRP, as well as conventional PVC and PVC/DOP
27 compound. Actually, extrudates free of surface instabilities can be achieved at
28 temperatures in the range 90-100°C.
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46 REFERENCES

- 47
48 1. J.S. Wang and K. Matyjaszewski, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **117** (29), 5614 (1995).
49
50 2. C. Granel, P. Dubois, R. Jerome, P. Teyssié, *Macromolecules*; **29** (27), 8576
51 (1996).
52
53 3. B.M. Rosen, V. Percec, *Chem. Rev.* **109**, 5069 (2009).
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 4. K. Matyjaszewski, S. Gaynor, J-S. Wang, *Macromolecules*; **28 (6)**, 2093
4 (1995).
- 5
6
7 5. P.B. Zetterlund, Y. Lagawa, M. Okubo, *Chem. Rev.* **108**, 3747 (2008).
- 8
9
10 6. V. Percec, A.V. Popov, E. Ramirez-Castillo, M. Monterio, B. Barboiou, O.
11 Weichold, A.D. Asandei and C.M. Mitchell, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **124 (18)**, 4940
12 (2002).
- 13
14
15 7. V. Percec, A.V. Popov, E. Ramirez-Castillo and O. Weichold, *J. Polym. Sci.*
16 *Part A, Polym. Chem.* **42 (24)**, 6364 (2004).
- 17
18
19 8. V. Percec, T. Guliashvili, A.V. Popov, U.S. Patent Appl. Publ. 2005/0131186,
20 Chem. Abstr. **143**, 60398. (2005).
- 21
22
23 9. N. Rocha, J.F.J. Coelho, B. Barros, P.M.L. Cardoso, P.M. Gonçalves, M.H.
24 Gil, J.T. Guthrie, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* **127**, 3407 (2013).
- 25
26
27 10. V. Percec, E. Ramirez-Castillo, A.V. Popov, L.A. Hinojosa-Falcon and T.
28 Guliashvili, *J. Polym. Sci. Part A, Polym. Chem.* **43**, 2178 (2005).
- 29
30
31 11. J.F.J Coelho, A.M.F.P. Silva, A.V. Popov, V. Percec, M.V. Abreu, P.M.O.F.
32 Gonçalves and M.H. Gil, *J. Polym. Sci. Part A, Polym. Chem.* **44**, 3001 (2006).
- 33
34
35 12. N. Overbergh, G. Weinand and G. Smets, *J. Polym. Sci. Part A, Polym.*
36 *Chem.* **16**, 3107 (1978).
- 37
38
39 13. A.M. Zdilar and R.I. Tanner, *J. Rheol.* **38(4)**, 909 (1994).
- 40
41
42 14. S.J. Guerrero and A. Keller, *J. Macromol. Sci.* **B20(2)**, 167 (1981).
- 43
44
45 15. J.F.J. Coelho, P. Alves, J. Monteiro, M.M.C.A. Castro, M. Abreu, P.
46 Gonçalves, M.H. Gil, *Mater. Sci. Forum* , **514-516**, 975 (2006).
- 47
48
49 16. J.F.J. Coelho, M. Carreira, P.M.O.F. Gonçalves, A.V. Popov and M.H. Gil, *J.*
50 *Vinyl & Additive Tech.* **12(4)**, 156 (2006).
- 51
52
53 17. J.F.J. Coelho, M. Carreira, A.V. Popov, P.M.O.F. Gonçalves, M.H. Gil, *Eur.*
54 *Polym. J.* **42**, 2313 (2006).
- 55
56
57 18. T. Rehm, *J. Vinyl & Additive Tech.* **4(4)**, 259 (1998).
- 58
59
60 19. J. Yuan, M. Pan, X. Wang and L. Zhang, *Polym. Eng. Sci.* **47(7)**, 996
(2007).

- 1
2
3 20. M. Pan and L. Zhang, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* **90**, 643 (2003).
4
5 21. S.F. Bates, *Science* **251**, 898 (1991).
6
7 22. V. Percec, A.V. Popov, E. Ramirez-Castillo, O. Weichold, *J. Polym. Sci. Part*
8 *A, Polym. Chem.* **41**, 3283 (2003).
9
10 23. J. Bandrup, E.H. Immergut and E.A. Grulke, *Polymer Handbook*, 4th Ed.
11 John Wiley New York (1999), VII, 675.
12
13 24. W.W. Graessley, *Polymeric Liquids & Networks: Structure and Properties*.
14 Garland Science New York and London (2004).
15
16 25. M.J. Folkes, *Processing, Structure and Properties of Block Copolymers*,
17 Elsevier Applied Science Publishers, London and New York (1989).
18
19 26. C.I. Chung and J.C. Gale, *J. Polym. Sci.* **14(6)**, 1149 (1976).
20
21 27. E.V. Gouinlock, R.S. Porter, *Polym. Eng. Sci.* **17(8)**, 534 (1977).
22
23 28. C.I. Chung, M.I. Lin, *J. Polym. Sci.: Polym. Phys.* **16(3)**, 545 (1978).
24
25 29. C.D. Han, J. Kim, J.K. Kim, *Macromolecules* **22**, 383 (1989).
26
27 30. W.W. Graessley *Polymeric Liquids & Networks: Dynamics and Rheology*.
28 Garland Science New York and London (2008).
29
30 31. M.B. Kossuth, D.C. Morse and F.S. Bates, *J. Rheo.* **43(1)**, 167 (1999).
31
32 32. C. Bonnebat and A.J. De Vries, *Polym. Eng. Sci.* **18(10)**, 825 (1978).
33
34 33. J. Zou, L. Su, F. You, G. Chen and S. Guo, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* **121**, 1725
35 (2011).
36
37 34. E.A. Collins, *Pure Appl. Chem.* **49**, 581 (1977).
38
39 35. G. Butters, *Particulate Nature of PVC*. Applied Science, Publishers Ltd.
40 London (1982).
41
42 36. J.J. Peña, G.M. Guzmán and A. Santamaría, *Mater. Chem. Phys.* **9**, 513
43 (1983).
44
45 37. J.J. Peña, A. Santamaría and G.M. Guzmán, *Eur. Polym. J.* **20(1)**, 49
46 (1984).
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 38. M. Yamaguchi, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* **82**, 1277 (2001).
4
5 39. J. Lyngaae-Jorgensen, *Makromol. Chem., Macromol. Symp.* **29**,109 (1989).
6
7 40. R. Bird, R.C. Armstrong and O. Hassager, *Dynamics of Polymeric Liquids;*
8 *Fluid Mechanics*, John Wiley & Sons (1987).
9
10 41. G.V. Vinogradov and A. Ya Malkin, *Rheology of Polymers: Viscoelasticity*
11 *and flow of Polymers*, Mir Publishers, Moscow (1980).
12
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Legends for the Tables

Table I.- Molecular parameters and glass transition temperatures (obtained by DMTA) of the investigated samples.

Table II.- Summary of DSC results.

Legends for the Figures

Figure 1.- 500 MHz ^1H NMR spectra of : (—) 25PVC-50PBA-25PVC copolymer; (—) free-radical PVC in THF- d_8 at room temperature.

Figure 2.- Loss tangent as a function of temperature for PVC-PBA-PVC copolymers, as well as PVC and PBA homopolymers.

Figure 3.- Elastic modulus (G') (full symbols) and viscous modulus (G'') (open symbols) as a function of frequency at $T = 180^\circ\text{C}$, for PVC and PBA homopolymers and 40PVC/20PBA/40PVC.

Figure 4.- Differential scanning calorimetry results of PVC and PVC-PBA-PVC copolymers. From top to bottom: 25PVC/50PBA/25PVC; 30PVC/40PBA/30PVC; 35PVC/30PBA/35PVC; 40PVC/20PBA/40PVC and PVC.

Figure 5.- Viscosity as a function of shear rate for PVC and triblock copolymers at different temperatures a) PVC obtained through Living radical polymerization at the indicated temperatures b) 35PVC/30PBA/35PVC; from top to bottom 100°C , 120°C , 140°C , 160°C , 180°C and 190°C .

Figure 6.- Arrhenius-like plots, $\ln \eta$ versus $1/T$, at a constant shear rate of 100 s^{-1} . The lines correspond to the fitting of the data to Equation 1, with one or two E_a values. From top to bottom: PVC; 40PVC/20PBA/40PVC; 35PVC/30PBA/35PVC; 30PVC/40PBA/30PVC and 25PVC/50PBA/25PVC.

Figure 7.- TEM image of the sample 25PVC/50PBA/25PVC.

Figure 8.- Viscosity as a function of shear rate for PVC and the copolymers at the lowest temperature ($T = 160^\circ\text{C}$) allowed for PVC. A plasticized commercial

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3 PVC (35% DOP) is included for comparison purposes.
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6 Figure 9.- Microphotographs of extrudate surfaces: a) PVC obtained at T=160°C
7 and a shear rate of 10 s⁻¹ b) 40PVC/20PBA/40PVC copolymer obtained at
8 T=100°C and a shear rate of 300 s⁻¹.
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Table I

Material	%BA	Tg(°C)	GPC		
			Mn (g/mole)	Mw (g/mole)	IP
PVC SET-DTLRP		88	64,700	162,200	2.5
40PVC/20PBA/40PVC	22	- / 86	110,800	274,700	2.5
35PVC/30PBA/35PVC	32	0 / 78	89,200	235,700	2.6
30PVC/40PBA/25PVC	42	-8 / 80	100,500	267,700	2.7
25PVC/50PBA/25PVC	52	-4 / 78	81,500	225,400	2.8
PVC FRP		90	85,500	176,200	2.1

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Table II

Material	T _{m1} (°C)	T _{m2} (°C)	χ _{PVC} (%)
PVC SET-DTLRP	127±0.5	190±0.2	9±1
40PVC/20PBA/40PVC	126±0.1	186±0.3	10±1.2
35PVC/30PBA/35PVC	128±0.4	185±0.4	7±0.2
30PVC/40PBA/25PVC	128±0.2	181±2.2	10±1.2
25PVC/50PBA/25PVC	128±0.1	186±0.3	7±0.3

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Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

a) Viscosity- shear rate LRP PVC

b) Viscosity-shear rate 35PVC/30PBA/35PVC

Figure 6

Figure 7

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Figure 8

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Figure 9

a)

b)

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Figure 7. TEM image of the sample 25PVC/50PBA/25PVC
254x190mm (96 x 96 DPI)

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Figure 9.- Microphotographs of extrudate surfaces: a) PVC obtained at T=160°C and a shear rate of 10 s⁻¹

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31 Figure 9.- Microphotographs of extrudate surfaces. b) 40PVC/20PBA/40PVC copolymer obtained at $T=100^{\circ}\text{C}$
32 and a shear rate of 300 s^{-1}
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